

TETR ARCHs

Transforming Data Reuse in Archaeology

Deliverable 5.3

Community Critiques & Critical Friends

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Summary

This Deliverable 5.3, titled *Community Critiques & Critical Friends*, reflects on the community workshops held during the first year of the TETRARCHS project. In particular, we discuss the challenges presented by the original planned workshop formats, and how we responded by adapting our strategy for subsequent engagement activities. We close with a series of recommendations developed as a result of this work, to guide future such initiatives within TETRARCHS.

1. Introduction

At the outset of the project, Task 5.4 and associated Deliverable 5.2 proposed to hold up to three closed workshops with local communities living within 10km of the relevant archaeological sites. The rationale was that such workshops would provide a structured forum for critical dialogue, ensuring that local values and perspectives were incorporated into the data collection and reuse processes. However, as we undertook our first field experiments, it became clear that the original plan presented several practical challenges. Many of our excavations take place in remote areas, and although there is a strong sense of local ownership or affinity for the sites, the people who care about them are sometimes scattered across a wider region, living beyond the 10km radius defined in the project plan. In addition, while there was enthusiasm for local participation and hands-on activities, the more formal structure of the proposed workshops did not always encourage the level of feedback or open dialogue we had hoped to get. As a result, coordinating these sessions in a way that captured meaningful local perspectives proved more difficult than anticipated.

This deliverable reports (1) how we adapted our engagement strategy to respond to these limitations, (2) how these adjustments allowed us to gather richer feedback, and (3) how this feedback has influenced ongoing experimentation within WP5.

2. Original Format and First Trial (Västra Vång Workshop)

At the beginning of the project, as described in D5.2 Part 1, the original workshop format was tested by Lund University during its field investigation at Västra Vång. With the support from the Blekinge Museum (the university's associate project partner), a group of participants was selected, including museum staff and members of the local community, many of whom were volunteers who had supported previous excavation campaigns. Despite the remote location of the site, which limited the possibility of engaging people living within a 10 km radius, many of the selected participants had longstanding connections to the site through heritage activities, professional work, or personal memory.

In preparation for the workshop, participants received access to an interactive story created in the AIR platform, along with instructions on how to explore the system. They were asked to read the story in advance. The workshop, held at the Blekinge Museum on November 7, 2023, began with a collective demonstration of the narrative interface, showing how the textual content, the 3D canvas-based layout, and archaeological data were interlinked.

Participants were then asked to respond to a short set of open-ended questions:

1. What words or phrases come to mind after each paragraph?
2. What other keywords do you associate with this story? Does it evoke any feelings or memories?
3. What tags would you use to make this story easier to find online?

After this exercise, the second part of the workshop focused on critically assessing the system. Participants were encouraged to reflect on whether the digital story and underlying data met their expectations. This led to constructive feedback, much of it unprompted. A recurring critique was the absence of sufficient visual material within the narrative structure. Although the system had been

designed to rely solely on data collected during excavation or preserved in the archive, it became immediately clear that this approach limited the capacity to tell richer or more meaningful stories.

This lesson prompted a rethinking of how archaeological documentation might be supported. In the following field experiment at Toumba Serron (see D5.2 Part 2), we began integrating alternative types of media into the documentation process, including photographs of fieldwork activities and sound recordings, but also started looking into strategies on how to incorporate in our archives material produced by artists joining the field campaign and documenting the investigation process. These additions aimed to reflect the excavation as both a scientific and a social process. While the initial workshop model succeeded in highlighting system limitations, the formal structure did not encourage fluid participation. Participants appeared hesitant, and discussions remained relatively constrained.

3. Rethinking the Format: From Closed Workshops to Context-Responsive Strategies

The rigid structure of the workshop format proved too limiting. Participants often felt uncomfortable expressing critiques in a formal setting. To address these limitations, the team at Lund University, in consultation with the Blekinge Museum, decided to adopt a more flexible approach to collecting feedback. Instead of organising formal appointments, we developed context-specific strategies to facilitate more informal engagement. Our aim was to create an informal and non-stressful environment that would enable participants to share reflections and critique.

One of the main strategies tested during the second year of the project was the anonymous questionnaire, implemented as part of the experiment at the rock art site of Hästhallen. Participants were primarily volunteers from the Swedish Cultural Heritage Federation (*Sveriges hembygdsförbund*) and museum staff, engaged directly in the 3D documentation process. Afterwards, they were invited to explore the resulting 3D model via the AIR platform and respond to a five-question online survey (for more detailed information about the experiment, see D5.2 Part 2).

The responses yielded several insights. First, they confirmed the value of participatory documentation: volunteers reported a stronger connection to the site and an enhanced understanding of the archaeological material. Second, feedback revealed that the system used to publish the results (AIR) was difficult to navigate, which limited engagement. Interestingly, participants seemed not to criticise the dataset itself but rather the platform's interface accessibility and structure.

Although fewer than half of the participants completed the questionnaire, the anonymous format created a safer space for expressing direct feedback. This was especially valuable in contexts where formal critique might be culturally sensitive or institutionally constrained. It also reinforced the need for critical engagement strategies that are tailored to each field context. As demonstrated across our experiments, every site and community operates under different political, cultural, and logistical conditions. Therefore, a one-size-fits-all format is not effective.

At Toumba Serron, informal conversations during fieldwork, coupled with more formal training workshops and evaluation sessions for team members, played a crucial role in shaping the project's digital tools and workflows. These workshops were designed to ensure that all team members were equipped with the knowledge and skills needed to engage with the evolving digital platforms.

In addition, broader TETRARCHs interventions at Toumba Serron during the 2024 field season were centred around the development and implementation of a linked-data-driven digital infrastructure, primarily through the AIR system, which acted as a central hub for the integration of various forms of data. There was a focus here on incorporating creative practices into the digital workflows, through close work with embedded artists and storytelling workshops with various local stakeholders. For example, digital tools were adapted to not only capture the technical data from the excavation but also integrate more interpretative and artistic outputs created during the fieldwork, such as visual documentation, emotive photography and audio as well as storytelling workshops. These creative contributions were connected to the archaeological data in the system, making the resulting dataset richer and more multidimensional.

TETRARCHs interventions were dynamic and flexible, driven by a collaborative approach that aimed to ensure the digital tools were not only effective in managing archaeological data but also capable of supporting the interdisciplinary nature of the project, bridging the gap between archaeology, art, and the local community.

This collaborative environment allowed the Lund team to not only develop and modify the tools in real time, but also immediately implement and adapt them based on direct feedback from both the team and local participants. The ability to reflexively adjust the digital workflows as new insights emerged during these hands-on training sessions was instrumental in refining the system, ensuring it was both functionally effective and culturally resonant with the community's values and expectations. These workshops, therefore, facilitated a dynamic, iterative process where tools could be continually fine-tuned, fostering a responsive and adaptive approach to archaeological documentation.

In the case study on the Iron Age settlements in the Pivka region of western Slovenia, which focussed on a landscape-sized case study based on airborne LiDAR data, the approach was based on what is best described as a mixture of workshop and interviews. We developed this approach in previous field seasons as the best method for teaching LiDAR in archaeology and adapted it for the purposes of the TETRARCHs field experiment. As above, this approach also fosters a collaborative environment necessary to create a feedback loop to improve the data capture models while at the same time providing a teaching environment.

Moving forward, each case study in WP5 will continue to define its own mechanisms for eliciting critique and community input. Some approaches may include informal conversations and structured discussions during fieldwork, collaborative annotations, or embedded reflection activities. While some of these strategies have already proven more successful than others, all contribute to refining the documentation tools and workflows developed within the project.

4. Gathering and Utilising Feedback

Contrary to the idea of identifying a fixed strategy for community critique, WP5's experience showed that strategies had to be adapted case by case. Rather than pre-establishing a universal methodology, we found ourselves reflecting retroactively on how feedback had emerged spontaneously during different stages of experimentation. It was only during internal discussions within WP5—prompted by the need to compile this deliverable—that we began to trace and recognise the value of these informal and context-specific approaches.

Several key practices emerged across different case studies:

- **Embedded Observation and On-Site Interaction:** At Hästhallen, spontaneous reflections surfaced as volunteers cleaned and observed the site during 3D scanning. Their insights were gathered informally through conversation, not structured feedback forms.
- **Anonymous Questionnaires:** Also at Hästhallen, the AIR platform was used to distribute a five-question survey. Though the response rate was below 50%, the anonymity created a safer space for critique, particularly around the limitations of the web interface.
- **Follow-up Conversations and Informal Review:** Feedback was often gathered after formal experiments had concluded, through personal communication, email exchanges, or opportunistic follow-ups initiated by team members or partners (such as Blekinge Museum staff and in the approach taken at Toumba Serron).
- **Cross-WP Reflections:** During WP5 and WP4 bi-weekly meetings, feedback was discussed collectively and critically. This helped identify themes not immediately apparent in the raw feedback (e.g., platform limitations, participant hesitancy).
- **Adaptation During Experimentation:** Sometimes, as at Toumba Serron, new forms of feedback collection were introduced mid-experiment when it became apparent that the original approach was not yielding sufficient insight.

These adaptive strategies highlight that community critique in archaeological documentation is less about finding a universal method and more about maintaining flexibility and sensitivity to the social and physical context of each site. While unplanned, this reactive approach has proven valuable and will serve as a foundation for more formally embedding responsive critique mechanisms in future work.

5. Collaborative Review and Iteration

All feedback collected via these customised approaches was discussed in our regular WP4 and WP5 meetings, which occur every two weeks. During these meetings:

- We review the feedback for emerging themes, concerns, and suggestions.
- We reflect on how these insights might influence the methodologies and objectives of upcoming experiments.
- We incorporate the most relevant points directly into the planning and design of the next experiment cycle, ensuring that local voices continually shape our work.

6. Conclusion

By shifting from a rigid “closed workshop” format to a more flexible, localised engagement strategy, we have been able to secure deeper, more meaningful critiques from community members and volunteers. While this approach diverges from the original project description, it ensures that local values are embedded in the data and workflows in a way that aligns better with the realities of archaeological fieldwork and the preferences of participating communities. The resulting insights have become a central element in shaping subsequent experiments and will directly inform the final report.

7. Recommendations

The following recommendations draw on insights gathered from the 2023-2024 field experiments and community critique activities undertaken as part of TETRARCHs Work Package 5. They reflect the project’s shift from a pre-planned model of structured workshops to more flexible, context-sensitive forms of engagement. These revised approaches have proven more effective in embedding local values within archaeological data workflows, supporting the project’s broader aim to foster inclusive, ethically grounded digital practices. The recommendations outlined below are intended to guide the 2024 field seasons and contribute to the final synthesis of project outcomes.

1. Adopt Flexible, Context-Specific Strategies for Community Engagement

Building on the experiences of the 2023 field experiments, we recommend that community engagement activities in 2024 continue to move away from rigid, pre-defined workshop formats. While the original intention to hold closed workshops with community members was well-founded, our practical experiences have demonstrated that such formats often inhibit open dialogue and can be difficult to implement meaningfully in remote or dispersed communities. Instead, future engagement should remain responsive to local conditions, allowing each case study team to determine the most appropriate and effective ways to gather community feedback and foster dialogue. This might include informal discussions during fieldwork, in-situ reflections, or opportunistic conversations that emerge naturally in the course of excavation and documentation.

Action: Allow each case study team to define its own engagement approach, suited to the site’s context.

2. Embed Feedback Collection Within Daily Field Practice

One of the most valuable lessons from the 2023 season was the recognition that meaningful critique and reflection often occur spontaneously, outside of formalised settings. By embedding mechanisms for observation, dialogue, and feedback directly into the rhythm of fieldwork, teams can create space for participants to reflect on the tools and approaches being used. These reflections should be actively documented and shared within the project to inform ongoing refinements. Team members should be encouraged to see community interaction as part of their research activity, not an adjunct to it.

Action: Continue to integrate informal feedback activities directly into daily fieldwork routines.

3. Make Use of Anonymous and Low-Threshold Feedback Tools

In contexts where direct critique may be difficult or culturally sensitive, anonymous tools such as brief surveys have proven useful in eliciting honest responses. These should continue to be employed where appropriate, with care taken to ensure they are accessible, easy to use, and do not place undue burden on participants. Where digital systems are used to distribute feedback forms, teams should remain attentive to accessibility issues and consider alternative formats when necessary.

Action: Where appropriate, continue using simple anonymous surveys and adapt them for accessibility where needed.

4. Continue to Work with Embedded Creative Practitioners

The involvement of TETRARCHS' resident creative practitioners has played an important role in broadening the scope of what constitutes valuable archaeological documentation. Through their work, we have been able to capture emotional, sensory, and interpretative aspects of the field experience that are often absent from traditional records. We recommend continuing to support and collaborate with these artists to explore how creative practices can generate new forms of critique and help embed community perspectives in the digital workflows. Their presence also contributes to a more inclusive understanding of the excavation as both a scientific and cultural process.

Action: Maintain collaboration with creative practitioners to enrich documentation and community input.

5. Maintain Flexible Coordination Across Work Packages

While the formal structure of regular WP4 and WP5 meetings will not be sustained into the final phases of the project, close coordination remains essential. Liaison between teams will continue on an as-needed basis to ensure that insights from fieldwork and experimentation are shared in a timely way and that feedback loops between tool development and field testing remain responsive and effective.

Action: Liaise between WPs as needed to share feedback and inform tool refinement.

6. Develop Best Practice Guidelines for Reflexive and Responsible Data Stewardship

Drawing on the diverse approaches trialled across the case studies, we recommend that the TETRARCHS project now works towards synthesising a set of best practice guidelines for implementing a 'virtuous circle' of archaeological data stewardship. These guidelines, which will form part of the final project deliverables, should reflect the adaptive, iterative, and community-sensitive approaches developed during the project and provide a framework for others seeking to embed similar values in their own digital workflows.

Action: Develop cross-WP best practice guidelines for ethical, responsive data workflows to be included in final project deliverables.

7. Consider Accessibility in Digital Tools, Where Feasible

While feedback on platforms such as AIR has highlighted issues with navigation and accessibility, addressing these concerns remains a longer-term goal. Enhancements to usability and interface design should be pursued where time and resources allow, but it is acknowledged that such improvements may extend beyond the current scope of TETRARCHs. Nonetheless, where possible, future iterations of these tools should aim to accommodate a broader user base, including non-specialist audiences.

Action: Improve digital platform accessibility where feasible, recognising resource limits.

8. Ensure Data is Open and FAIR Through Stakeholder Liaison

As part of our commitment to responsible data management, we recommend that teams continue to liaise with relevant national authorities, curatorial bodies, and archival institutions to ensure that data produced through TETRARCHs fieldwork is made openly accessible and aligned with FAIR (Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, and Reusable) principles. This will help maximise the long-term value of the project's outputs and support the integration of these datasets into broader heritage infrastructures.

Action: Continue to liaise with curatorial stakeholders to ensure TETRARCHs data is Open and FAIR.

TETRARCHs is making archaeological data accessible to a wider range of people.

The project explores how data from excavations and post-excavation research can be used and reused for educational, creative, and other life-enriching purposes. We work collaboratively across a variety of communities to experiment with storytelling about the past.

For heritage professionals, we create new resources for developing and measuring the effectiveness of archaeological data for storytelling.

For memory institutions like museums and cultural centres, we create reference materials to support you using these new resources for storytelling.

For creatives and local citizens, we will create a platform where you can search for and experiment with storytelling about the past.

Get in touch:

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